

How to Obtain a Right to Help at Home for Seniors With Disabilities

There is a significant increase in the share of the elderly population, as one of the socially vulnerable groups in the total population. [According to Yosef Meystel](#), this increases the need for social care and social services that depend on the quality of life of older people.

Professional home help and care services for the elderly, people with disabilities and children with disabilities and all those who need such assistance and have the ability to finance themselves are provided by numerous companies. Such companies can provide home help and care for the individual and the needs that his family can not afford because of today's modern lifestyle.

[On Crunchbase](#) you can find out about joining the Aperia Care program that enables older people to have a longer life span and stay in their own home through helping them live their daily lives directly in their homes.

Presented by Meystel, the program is intended for persons older than 65 years of age (exceptionally younger than 65 if they are people with severely disadvantaged health status, chronic illness, hard-moving or immobile persons), persons with reduced functional abilities, older people who live alone without the help of younger family members or close relatives (single-parent households), persons with a low socioeconomic status, people with a severe disorder, and persons not covered by existing forms of care (various forms of home help, such as social welfare rights, other forms of care through non-governmental organization or the like).

Customer service programs are free, including: organizing meals, helping with housekeeping and landscaping, helping to maintain personal hygiene and basic health care, talking and socializing, mediating between older people and institutions related to the realization of different rights.

For more information or engaging in the program, contact the Yosef Meystel from Aperia Care, either on his [LinkedIn](#), [Twitter](#) or [Facebook](#) profile.